

CELLULAR FREQUENCY-HOPPING CDMA SYSTEMS

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Abstract - The potential performance of a cellular frequency-hopping code-division multiple-access system is evaluated for both the forward and reverse links. The effects of sectorization, the number of mobile users per sector, spatial diversity, the number of frequency channels, and the thermal noise are studied. The performance advantage of separated orthogonal frequency-hopping patterns, which eliminate the effects of spectral splatter, is demonstrated.

1. INTRODUCTION

Compared with the alternatives, code-division multiple access (CDMA) is advantageous for cellular networks because it eliminates the need for frequency and timeslot coordination among cells, allows complete frequency reuse in all cells, and can fully exploit intermittent voice signals and sectorization. The two principal types of CDMA are direct-sequence CDMA and frequency-hopping CDMA. A major advantage of frequency hopping is that it can be implemented over a much larger frequency band than it is possible to implement direct-sequence spreading, and the band can be noncontiguous. Another major advantage is that frequency hopping provides resistance to multiple-access interference while not requiring power control to prevent the near-far problem. In direct-sequence systems, accurate power control is crucial but becomes much less effective as the carrier frequency is increased [1]. These two advantages of frequency hopping will be decisive in many applications.

2. HOPPING PARAMETERS

The duration of a hop, denoted by T_h , is equal to the sum of the dwell time T_d and the switching time T_{sw} . The *dwell time* is the duration of the frequency-hopping pulse during which the channel symbols are transmitted. The *switching time* is equal to the dead time, when no signal is present, plus the rise and fall times of a pulse. Even if the switching time is absent in the transmitted signal, it will be present in the dehopped signal in the receiver because of the imperfect synchronization of received and receiver-generated waveforms. The nonzero switching time, which may include an intentional guard time, decreases the transmitted symbol duration T_s . If T_{so} is the symbol duration in the absence of frequency hopping, then $T_s = T_{so} (T_d/T_h)$. The reduction in symbol duration expands the transmitted spectrum and thereby reduces the number of frequency channels within a fixed total hopping band. Since the receiver

filtering will ensure that rise and fall times of pulses have durations on the order of T_s , the practical assumption that $T_{sw} > T_s$ is made in the subsequent analysis. Thus, each interferer transmits in at most one frequency channel during the reception of a single symbol of the desired signal.

It is assumed that the receiver transfer function following the dehopping is approximately rectangular with bandwidth B , which is equal to the bandwidth of a frequency channel. Let M denote the number of carriers and frequency channels in a hopset, W the total bandwidth occupied by the M channels, and F_s the minimum separation between carriers in a hopset. For frequency hopping to enable a signal to escape stationary narrowband interference and jamming, it is desirable that $F_s \geq B$ so that the frequency channels are nearly spectrally disjoint.

Spectral splatter is the interference produced in frequency channels other than the one being used by a frequency-hopping pulse. Usually only adjacent channels produce a significant amount of spectral splatter in a channel. The *adjacent splatter ratio* K is the ratio of the power due to spectral splatter from an adjacent channel to the corresponding power that arrives at the receiver in that channel. For example, if B is the bandwidth of a frequency channel that includes 97 percent of the signal power and $F_s \geq B$, then no more than 1.5 percent of the power from a transmitted pulse can enter an adjacent channel on one side of the frequency channel used by the pulse; therefore, $K \leq 0.015$. A given maximum value of K can be reduced by an increase in F_s , but eventually the value of M must be reduced if W is fixed. As a result, the rate at which users hop into the same channel increases. This increase may cancel any improvement due to the reduction of the spectral splatter. The opposite procedure (reducing F_s and B so that more frequency channels become available) increases not only the spectral splatter but also signal distortion and intersymbol interference, so the amount of useful reduction is limited.

In a cellular network, each base station assigns separate directional sector antennas or separate outputs of a phased array to cover disjoint angular sectors in both the transmitting and receiving modes. Typically, there are three sectors, and $2\pi/3$ radians are in each angular sector. The mobile antennas are assumed to be omnidirectional. Ideal sector antennas have uniform gain over the covered sector and negligible sidelobes. With these antennas, only mobiles in the covered sector can cause multiple-access interference on a reverse link from a mobile to a base station, and the

number of interfering signals on the link is reduced by a factor s approximately equal to the number of sectors. Only the antenna serving a cell sector oriented toward a mobile can cause multiple-access interference on the forward link from the controlling base station to a mobile. Therefore, the number of interfering signals is reduced approximately by a factor s on both the forward and reverse links.

Spatial diversity may be obtained through the deployment of L antennas in each mobile and L antenna elements for each sector antenna of each base station. The antennas are separated from each other enough that the fading of both the desired signal and the interfering signals at one antenna is independent of the fading at the other antennas. A few wavelengths are adequate for a mobile because it tends to receive superpositions of reflected waves arriving from many random angles. Many wavelengths separation may be necessary for a base station located at a high position, and polarization diversity may sometimes be a more practical means of obtaining diversity.

In a cellular network, the frequency-hopping patterns can be chosen so that at any given instant in time, the frequencies of the users within a cell sector are all different and, hence, the received signals are all orthogonal if the mobile transmissions are properly synchronized. Exact synchronization on the forward link is possible because a common timing is available. The advancing or retarding of the transmit times of the mobiles enables the arrival times at the base station of the reverse-link signals to be synchronized. The switching time or guard time between frequency-hopping pulses must be large enough to ensure that neither a small synchronization error nor multipath signals can subvert the orthogonality. The appropriate transmit times of a mobile can be determined from position information provided by the global positioning system and the known location of the base station. Alternatively, the transmit times can be determined from arrival-time measurements at the base station that are sent to the mobile. These measurements may be based on the adaptive thresholding [2] of the leading and/or trailing edges of a sequence of frequency-hopping pulses.

Let N_s denote the number of mobiles assigned to a cell sector. To ensure orthogonality of N_s received signals within a cell sector, a simple procedure is to generate a periodic frequency-hopping pattern that does not repeat until all the carrier frequencies in a hopset of size $M \geq N_s$ have been used. Mobile n is assigned this pattern with a delay of $n-1$ hop durations, where $n = 1, 2, \dots, N_s$. If the patterns associated with different sectors are all drawn from a set of one-coincidence sequences [3], then any two signals from different cells or sectors will collide in frequency at a base station at most once during the period of the hopping patterns. However, the use of one-coincidence sequences throughout a network requires frequency planning, which may be too costly in some applications.

It is possible to ensure not only the orthogonality of N_s signals in a sector but also that the received carrier frequencies in any two patterns are separated by at least vB so that the spectral splatter is greatly reduced or negligible. Let $k = 1, 2, \dots, M$ label the hopset frequencies in ascending order. Suppose that a frequency-hopping pattern is generated that does not repeat until all the carrier frequencies in a hopset of size $M \geq vN_s$ have been used. When mobile 1 hops to frequency k , mobile n hops to frequency $[k + v(n-1)]$ modulo M . Frequency-hopping signals that use frequencies determined by this procedure are called *separated orthogonal signals*. Choosing $v = 2$ will generally be adequate because spectral splatter from channels that are not adjacent will be nearly always insignificant if a spectrally compact data modulation is used.

Frequency-hopping CDMA networks largely avoid the near-far problem by continually changing the carrier frequencies so that frequency collisions become brief, unusual events. Thus, power control in a frequency-hopping CDMA network is unnecessary, and all mobiles may transmit at the same power level. Simulation results [4] indicate that even perfect power control typically increases system capacity by only a small amount. There are good reasons to forego this slight potential advantage and not use power control. The required overhead may be excessive. If geolocation of mobiles is done by using measurements at two or more base stations, then the power control may result in significantly less signal power arriving at one or more base stations and the consequent loss of geolocation accuracy.

3. INTERFERENCE PROBABILITIES

Let d represent the *duty factor*, which is defined as the probability that an interferer using the same frequency will degrade the reception of a symbol. Thus, $d = p_1 p_2$ is the product of the probability p_1 that an interferer is transmitting and the probability p_2 that a significant portion of the interferer's transmitted waveform occurs during the symbol interval. The probability p_2 is upper bounded and well approximated by the probability that there is any overlap in time of the interference and the symbol interval. For synchronized frequency-hopping pulses, $p_2 = 1$. Since $T_{sw} > T_s$, it follows from elementary probability that for unsynchronized frequency-hopping pulses, $p_2 \approx (T_d + T_s)/T_h$. For voice communications with voice-activity detection, $p_1 = 0.4$ is a typical value.

Consider communications between a base station and a mobile assigned to sector A of a particular cell, as illustrated in Figure 1 for a hexagonal grid of cells. Because of orthogonality, no other signal in sector A will use the same carrier frequency at the same time and thereby cause interference in the transmission channel (current frequency channel) of either the reverse link or the forward link. Consider another sector covered by the sector antenna of sector

A, for example, sector B of Figure 1. Assuming that an interfering signal may independently use any frequency in the network hopset with equal probability, the probability that a mobile in the covered sector produces interference in the transmission channel of the reverse link and degrades a particular symbol is

$$p_m = \frac{dN_s}{M} . \quad (1)$$

This equation also gives the probability that a sector antenna serving another sector that is oriented toward the desired mobile degrades a symbol by producing interference in the transmission channel of the forward link. Because of orthogonality within each sector, no more than one signal from a sector will produce interference in the transmission channel of either the reverse or forward link. A sector with mobiles that may interfere with communications over a reverse link or a sector with an antenna that may produce interference over a forward link is called an *interfering sector*.

It is assumed that M is sufficiently large that we may neglect the fact that a channel at one of the ends of the total band has only one adjacent channel instead of two. Let $N_1 = 1$ if a signal from an interfering sector uses the transmission channel of communicators in sector A; let $N_1 = 0$ if it does not. The probability that $N_1 = 1$ is N_s/M . The $N_s - N_1$ interference signals from a sector that do not enter the transmission channel are assumed to be randomly distributed among the $M - 1$ frequency channels excluding the transmission channel. There are $\binom{M-1}{N_s-N_1}$ ways to

choose the channels with interference signals. There are $\binom{2}{1}$ ways to choose one of the adjacent channels and $\binom{M-3}{N_s-N_1-1}$ ways to choose $N_s - N_1 - 1$ channels with interference signals out of the $M - 3$ channels excluding both the transmission channel and the adjacent channels.

There are $\binom{M-3}{N_s-N_1-2}$ ways to choose both adjacent

Figure 1. Hexagonal grid of cells. Communicators are in sector A. Sector B is an interfering sector.

channels and $N_s - N_1 - 2$ channels with interference signals out of $M - 3$ channels. The probability that exactly one of the two adjacent channels with interference signals actually receives interference is $2 p_1(1 - p_1)$. Because of the sector synchronization, either all of the signals from a sector overlap a desired symbol with probability p_2 or none of them do. Therefore, the probability that a symbol is degraded by interference in exactly one of the adjacent channels of the communicators is

$$\begin{aligned} p_{a1} &= \frac{\binom{2}{1} \binom{M-3}{N_s-N_1-1}}{\binom{M-1}{N_s-N_1}} p_1 p_2 + \frac{\binom{M-3}{N_s-N_1-2}}{\binom{M-1}{N_s-N_1}} 2 p_1(1-p_1) p_2 \\ &= \frac{2d(N_s-N_1)}{(M-1)(M-2)} [M-2-p_1(N_s-N_1-1)] , \quad M \geq N_s . \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Similarly, the probability that a symbol is degraded by interference in both adjacent channels is

$$\begin{aligned} p_{a2} &= \frac{\binom{M-3}{N_s-N_1-2}}{\binom{M-1}{N_s-N_1}} p_1^2 p_2 \\ &= \frac{d p_1 (N_s - N_1) (N_s - N_1 - 1)}{(M - 1) (M - 2)} , \quad M \geq N_s . \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

For adjacent-channel interference from within sector A, p_{a1} and p_{a2} are given by the same equations with $N_1 = 1$ to reflect the fact that one of the mobiles is the communicating mobile.

Suppose that separated orthogonal frequency-hopping patterns with $v = 2$ are used. There is no adjacent-channel interference from sector A. If a signal from an interfering sector B uses the transmission channel so that $N_1 = 1$, an event with probability N_s/M , then the carrier separation of the signals generated in sector B ensures that there is no adjacent-channel interference from sector B. Suppose that no signal from sector B uses the transmission channel so that $N_1 = 0$. Interference in exactly one adjacent channel results if the transmission channel of the desired signal in sector A, which may be any of $M - N_s$ channels, is located at one of the two ends of the set of N_s separated channels being used in sector B, neglecting hopset end effects. It also results if the transmission channel is located between two separated channels of which only one is currently being used in sector B, again neglecting hopset end effects. Therefore, the probability that a symbol is degraded by interference in exactly one of the adjacent channels of the communicators is

$$\begin{aligned}
p_{a1} &= \left[\frac{2p_1}{M-N_s} + \frac{N_s-1}{M-N_s} p_1(1-p_1) \right] p_2 \\
&= \frac{d}{M-N_s} [(N_s-1)(1-p_1)+2], \quad M \geq 2N_s, \quad N_1 = 0.
\end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

Interference in both adjacent channels results if the transmission channel is located between two separated channels of sector B and both are being used, neglecting hopset end effects. Therefore, the probability that a symbol is degraded by interference in both adjacent channels is

$$p_{a2} = \frac{dp_1(N_s-1)}{M-N_s}, \quad M \geq 2N_s, \quad N_1 = 0. \tag{5}$$

4. PROPAGATION, ANTENNA, AND SIGNAL MODELS

In this paper, the propagation path losses are modeled as the result of power-law path losses, shadowing, and fading [5]. In the absence of shadowing and fading, the received signal power for communications over a fixed range r has an average value called the *area-mean power*, where the average is calculated over a specified geographic area. The power-law model assumes that the area-mean power has the form

$$P_a = P_0 \left(\frac{r}{R_0} \right)^{-\beta} \tag{6}$$

where P_0 is the power when the range is $r = R_0$, and β is the power law. A typical value of the power law for an urban area is $\beta = 4$. In the absence of fading, the received *local-mean power* fluctuates about the area-mean power due to *shadowing*, which is the effect of path-to-path differences in terrain profiles for paths of the same distance. On the basis of extensive empirical data, the local-mean power P_l is assumed to be lognormally distributed, which implies that

$$P_l = P_a 10^{-\xi/10} \tag{7}$$

where ξ is a zero-mean random variable with a normal distribution. The standard deviation of ξ is denoted by σ_ξ , which is expressed in decibels and is assumed to be the same for all mobiles. A straightforward derivation using (6) and (7) indicates that the probability distribution function of the normalized local-mean power, P_l/P_a , is

$$F(x) = 1 - \frac{1}{2} \operatorname{erfc} \left\{ \frac{a}{\sigma_\xi} \ln \left[x \left(\frac{r}{R_0} \right)^\beta \right] \right\} \tag{8}$$

where $\operatorname{erfc} \{ \}$ denotes the complementary error function, and $a = (10 \log_{10} e)/\sqrt{2}$. The fading causes a power fluctuation about the local-mean power.

The desired signal and the interfering signals are all assumed to experience independent Rayleigh fading and shadowing. The interference plus noise at each antenna

output is approximated by independent bandlimited white Gaussian noise, with equivalent power given by

$$\sigma_I^2 = \sigma_n^2 + \sum_{i=1}^N P_{ui} \tag{9}$$

where σ_n^2 is the thermal noise power, N is the number of active interfering users, and P_{ui} is the local-mean interference power received from user i . The Gaussian model is reasonable, especially for large numbers of interferers, because the interference signals are asynchronous, are expected to fade independently, and experience different Doppler shifts. The independence of antenna outputs is reasonable because each multipath component of a single interfering signal arrives with a different phase at each diversity antenna. The total interference power is approximately uniform (white) over the receiver passband following dehoppping if $BT_s \leq 1$. The L diversity antennas are assumed to be close enough to each other that the power-law path losses and shadowing are nearly the same, and thus the local-mean power from a single source is the same at each antenna.

Since minimum-shift keying (MSK) is a constant-envelope, spectrally compact modulation that is amenable to noncoherent demodulation and for other reasons [6], the data modulation is assumed to be MSK, and the demodulator is assumed to be a frequency discriminator. For postdetection diversity, the outputs of L discriminators are weighted and combined. The weighting is by the square of the envelope at the input to each discriminator. When the desired signal is fading and the channel parameters remain constant for a least one symbol duration, a calculation using the results of Adachi and Parsons [7] yields the symbol error probability

$$P_s = \frac{1}{2} \frac{(2L-1)!!}{L!} \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{2}{3} \alpha^2 \right)^L \left(\frac{P_d}{\sigma_I^2} \right)^{-L} \tag{10}$$

where P_d is the local-mean power of the desired signal and $\alpha = BT_s$. The information-bit error rate following hard-decision decoding can be calculated from P_s with well-known equations.

5. SIMULATION RESULTS

In the simulation, the spatial configuration consists of a hexagonal grid of cells with base stations at their centers. Each cell has a radius R_0 from its center to a corner. A central cell is surrounded by an inner concentric tier of 6 cells and an outer concentric tier of 12 cells, as depicted in Figure 1. Other tiers are assumed to generate insignificant interference in the central cell. An equal number of mobiles each transmitting at the same power level is located in each sector and served by that sector's antenna. This assumption is pessimistic since slightly improved performance may be possible if a mobile is served by the sector antenna

providing a signal with the least attenuation and hysteresis effects during handoffs are not too severe. Each signal transmitted by a sector antenna is allocated the same power. The set of frequency-hopping patterns used in each sector is assumed to be selected independently of the other sectors. Since the parameter R_0 in (6) and (8) is equal to the maximum communication range, P_0 is the minimum received area-mean power of a desired signal. The location of each mobile within a sector is assumed to be uniformly distributed.

In each simulation trial for communications in sector A of the central cell, the distance of the desired mobile is randomly selected according to the uniform distribution. The selected distance of the desired mobile is substituted into (8) as the value of r , and then (8) is used to randomly select the local-mean power of the desired signal at the receiver. Each transmitting and receiving beam produced by a sector antenna is assumed to have a constant gain over its sector and zero gain elsewhere.

For the reverse link of sector A, interference is assumed to arrive from mobiles within sector A, mobiles in the 6 sectors of the two cells in the inner tier that are covered by the beam of sector A, and mobiles in the 11 complete sectors and 2 half-sectors of the five cells in the outer tier completely or partially covered by the beam. Equations (1) to (5) are used to determine if a sector contains mobiles that produce power in the transmission channel or in one or both of the adjacent channels. If the sector does, then the locations of the three or fewer interfering mobiles are randomly selected according to the uniform distribution, and their distances from the central cell's base station are computed.

For the forward link of sector A, interference is assumed to arrive from the facing sector antenna of each cell in the two surrounding tiers. Equations (1) to (5) are used to determine if a signal generated by a sector antenna produces power in the transmission channel or the adjacent channels of the desired signal. If so, then the distance between the sector antenna and the desired mobile is computed.

If the power from an interferer enters the transmission channel, then the power level is randomly selected according to (8) with the appropriate distance substituted. If the power enters an adjacent channel, then the potential local-mean power level is first randomly selected via (8) and then multiplied by K to determine the net interference power P_{ui} that appears in (9). The shadowing parameter σ_y is assumed to be the same for all signals originating from all cells. The effects of P_0 and σ_n^2 are determined solely by the minimum area-mean signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), which is equal to P_0/σ_n^2 . Since only power ratios affect the performance, the numerical value of R_0 in the simulation is immaterial and can be set equal to unity.

Once the local-mean power levels and the noise power are calculated, the symbol error probability is calculated with

(9) and (10). Each simulation experiment was repeated for 20,000 trials, with different randomly selected mobile locations in each trial. The performance measure is the *spatial reliability*, which is defined as the fraction of trials for which P_s is less than a specified performance threshold E . The spatial reliability is essentially the probability that an outage does not occur. The value of P_d/σ_f^2 , the signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio (SINR), that corresponds to E can be obtained by inverting (10). The appropriate value of the threshold depends on the desired information-bit error probability and the error-correcting code.

Figures 2 to 5 depict the results of four simulation experiments for the reverse link of a cellular network. The figures plot spatial reliability as a function of N_s for various values of L , assuming MSK, three sectors, and that $\beta = 4$, $p_1 = 0.4$, $p_2 = 0.9$, $\sigma_y = 8$ dB, $E = 0.01$, $\alpha = 1$, and $K = 0.015$. The value of K results from assuming contiguous frequency channels so that $F_s = B$. The value of E corresponds to SINR = 10 dB and dual diversity.

Figure 2 provides a baseline with which other figures may be compared. For this figure, separated orthogonal frequency hopping with $v = 2$, $M = 100$, and minimum SNR = 30 dB are assumed. The figure illustrates the dramatic performance improvement provided by dual spatial diversity when Rayleigh fading occurs. Further increases in diversity yield diminishing returns. One can assess the impact of the spectral splatter in this example by setting $K = 0$ and observing the change in spatial reliability. The change is insignificant because by far the most potentially damaging splatter arises from mobiles in the same sector as the desired mobile, and the separated orthogonality has eliminated it.

Figure 3 shows the effect of using orthogonal rather than separated orthogonal frequency hopping. The performance loss is significant in this example and becomes more

Figure 2. Spatial reliability for reverse link, separated orthogonal hopping, $M = 100$, and minimum SNR = 30 dB.

Figure 3. Spatial reliability for reverse link, orthogonal hopping, $M = 100$, and minimum SNR = 30 dB.

Figure 4. Spatial reliability for reverse link, separated orthogonal hopping, $M = 200$, and minimum SNR = 30 dB.

pronounced as M decreases. When separated orthogonal frequency hopping is used and the spectral splatter is negligible, then the spatial reliability depends on the ratio $M_1 = Md$, rather than the parameters d and M separately. This ratio is called the *equivalent number of channels*. In Figure 2, $M_1 = 250$.

Figure 4 illustrates the effect of increasing M to 200, and hence increasing M_1 to 500. Let the *reverse-link capacity* C_r of a cellular network be defined as the maximum number of interfering mobiles per cell for which the spatial reliability exceeds 0.95. Figures 2 and 4 and other simulation results indicate that for three sectors per cell, dual diversity, and the other parameter values selected, the reverse-link capacity is $C_r \approx 0.108 M_1$ for $50 \leq M_1 \leq 1000$. This equation is sensitive to parameter variations. If the shadowing standard deviation σ_s is lowered to 6 dB, it is found

Figure 5. Spatial reliability for reverse link, separated orthogonal hopping, $M = 100$, and minimum SNR = 20 dB.

Figure 6. Spatial reliability for forward link, separated orthogonal hopping, $M = 100$, and minimum SNR = 30 dB.

that C_r increases by roughly 57 percent. Alternatively, if the threshold E is raised to 0.04, corresponding to SINR = 7 dB, it is found that C_r increases by roughly 59 percent.

Figure 5 illustrates the sensitivity of the network to a decrease in the minimum SNR, which may be due to a change in either P_0 or σ_n^2 . A substantial performance loss occurs when the minimum SNR is reduced to 20 dB, particularly for no spatial diversity or dual diversity. Other simulation results indicate that an increase in the minimum SNR beyond 30 dB barely improves performance.

The forward link of a cellular network is considered in Figure 6, where the models and parameter values are otherwise the same as in Figure 2. The performance is worse than for the reverse link because of the relative proximity of some of the interfering sector antennas to the desired mobile. The results for parameter variations on the

forward-link performance are analogous but inferior to those depicted in Figures 3 to 5. In contrast, the forward link in direct-sequence CDMA networks gives better performance than the reverse link because orthogonal signaling is only possible on the forward link. The forward-link capacity C_f , which is defined analogously to the reverse-link capacity, is $C_f \approx 0.072 M_1$ for $50 \leq M_1 \leq 1000$.

Compared with direct-sequence systems, frequency-hopping systems have a bandwidth advantage in that frequency over a large, possibly noncontiguous, spectral band is as practical as direct-sequence spreading over a much smaller, necessarily contiguous, spectral band. Even deprived of its bandwidth advantage, as well as power control and the use of one-coincidence codes, frequency-hopping CDMA can provide nearly the same multiple-access capacity as direct-sequence CDMA subject to realistic power-control imperfections. For a numerical example, consider a sectorized cellular network with shadowing standard deviation $\sigma_y = 6$ dB and $d = p_1 = 3/8$ due to the voice activity. A contiguous spectral band of bandwidth $W = 1.25$ MHz is occupied by the CDMA signals. The symbol rate is $1/T_s = 8$ kb/s so that the processing gains is 156.5 for direct-sequence CDMA and the number of frequency channels for frequency-hopping CDMA with $BT_s = 1$ is $M = 156$. For frequency-hopping CDMA, the minimum SNR is 20.94 dB. Similarly, for direct-sequence CDMA, it is assumed that P_0 is the area-mean power at all ranges when the power control is perfect; thus, the minimum SNR after despreading is 20.94 dB and corresponds to a minimum SNR equal to -1 dB before despreading. The reverse-link capacity C_r is calculated as the number of mobile users per cell that can be accommodated while maintaining a specified SINR with 95 percent probability. For frequency-hopping CDMA with a specified SINR = 10 dB, it is found that $C_r \approx 60$. For direct-sequence CDMA with dual diversity, a similar symbol error probability can be obtained with the SINR lowered to 7 dB because of the approximately 3-dB advantage due to the coherent demodulation that is assumed to be available for direct-sequence signals. Using the results of reference [8] for a specified SINR = 7 dB, it is found that $C_r \approx 60$ when the power-control error has a standard deviation equal to 2 dB.

For coherent demodulation of a signal that hops over a wide band to be a practical possibility in a fading environment, the dwell time must be large enough that a small portion of it can be dedicated to carrier synchronization. The degradation due to the dedicated portion and the occasional failure to achieve carrier synchronization for a frequency-hopping pulse must be less than the potential gain due to the coherent demodulation. If ideal coherent demodulation is assumed in the preceding example so that the specified SINR = 7 dB, then it is found that $C_r \approx 108$. This reverse-link capacity is obtained by direct-sequence CDMA with a specified SINR = 7 dB when the standard deviation of the power-control error is approximately 0.4 dB.

6. CONCLUSIONS

For a specified sectorization, diversity, and waveform, the capacity of a frequency-hopping CDMA network is approximately proportional to the equivalent number of frequency channels. Thus, a desired capacity can be attained by choosing a sufficiently large number of frequency channels. A major advantage of frequency hopping is that these channels do not have to be spectrally contiguous but can be scattered throughout a large spectral band. Another advantage is that power control is not required. Its absence allows a substantial reduction of system complexity and overhead cost and facilitates geolocation. Sectorization, orthogonality, and dual diversity are invaluable, but higher levels of diversity offer sharply decreasing gains. If spectral splatter is a problem, separated orthogonal signaling can be used to eliminate it. The overall limit on the capacity of a frequency-hopping CDMA network appears to be set more by the forward link than the reverse link.

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